

ENGAGING STUDENTS IN THE LESSON THROUGH THE USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING ENGLISH

Axmadjonova Rayxonabonu Abdulxamid qizi

Faculty of English philology, teaching methodology and translation studies

Student of 312th group, Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7367678>

ABSTRACT: The article first examines how information technology may be used to teach English. The issue of language acquisition is one that is crucial nowadays. The issue of learning English for communication purposes is particularly pressing right now as Uzbekistan integrates into the global community. For any educated individual or competent professional, knowing English is a need. It's challenging to learn the English language. There are given main information about engaging students in the lesson through the use of information and communication technologies in the process of learning English in main body.

Keywords: task-based language teaching, cognitive competence, language structures, language form, automaticity, experiential learning, Language, Methods, Information Technology, Internet, Distance Learning.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that when teaching a foreign language, the teacher faces a number of questions aimed at increasing the motivation of students to learn foreign languages, since an unfamiliar language, due to its initial misunderstanding, causes fear among students, and, therefore, at the initial stage, interest instantly disappears. to his study. Therefore, an important task of the teacher is to create an atmosphere that will arouse students' interest in studying it. A foreign language should be a new unknown world for the student, which he has to master. But how to create conditions conducive to the development of children's interest in foreign languages? This problem still remains unresolved. In the modern world, the creation of such conditions in a foreign language lesson is no longer a problem due to the widespread use of information technologies, which serve not only as a tool for increasing motivation, but can also be effectively used to familiarize students with new educational material, with new patterns of statements, as well as as

a subject for control. In a general sense, information and communication technologies are resources that are necessary for the collection, processing, storage and dissemination of this or that information. These include: computers and laptops, printers, scanners, cameras, camcorders, tape recorders, etc.

MAIN BODY

The problem of learning languages is very important today. Foreign languages are socially demanded, especially at the present time, when the progress in science and technology has led to an explosion of knowledge and has contributed to an overflow of information. Foreign languages are needed as the main and most efficient means of information exchange of the people of our planet. Georgia is integrating into the world community and the problem of learning English for the purpose of communication is especially urgent today. To know English is absolutely necessary for every educated person, for every good specialist. So, if in elementary school a foreign language lesson is mainly carried out in the form of a game that helps to avoid memorization, then at the middle and senior stages of education, when it comes to complex grammatical structures and students are already out of childhood, the game form is not appropriate. The question immediately arises: "How to attract the attention of middle and high school students?". Here, in order to create a real situation and activate all types of activities, it is simply necessary to use information technologies, with the help of which you can effectively work out all types of speech activities, as well as improve listening and reading skills. Often in foreign language lessons, the process of involving students in oral speech on various topics becomes simply not interesting for the students themselves. Therefore, the activity of their work is sharply reduced, which leads to the loss of the desire of children to have a conversation. However, when working with the use of computer resources, this is excluded, since students are familiar with the world of information technology and it occupies a dominant place in the system of their interests. An important feature of the use of a computer in the teaching and educational process in a foreign language is that it can become a student's "interlocutor", i.e., work in a communicative-directed dialogical mode and in a certain way, for example, using graphic means of speech, make up for the lack of a natural communicator, modeling and imitating his non-verbal and verbal behavior. It is also worth noting

that the teacher in such a lesson constantly maintains a high pace and activity of students, which helps to master much more information, while ICT can be used at any stage of the lesson. Moreover, these resources serve as a teacher, assistant and friend to students, and also help them open up and express themselves by creating various thematic multimedia projects.¹

So, with the help of information and communication technologies, during the internship, I entered material on the following topics: *“Food and Drinks”*, *“Rules and Regulations”* and *“The Weather”*. At the same time, thanks to the active use of thematic presentations, audio recordings and computer programs, it was possible to fully master and consolidate new lexical units in speech, introduce new grammatical phenomena, master the cliches of speech etiquette, develop sociocultural competence and listening skills. With the help of information and communication technologies, an English lesson becomes brighter and more interesting, which helps to focus the attention of students and thereby activate them, and, as a result, any material offered is easily absorbed, while a lesson based on these resources does not necessarily imply a non-standard lesson (lesson game), lesson-excursion, interview, etc.), it can also be a lecture with a visual multimedia presentation, as well as a test, that is, information and communication technologies have nothing to do with the arbitrariness and freedom of students, on the contrary, with their using it is easier for the teacher to systematize the educational process. Currently, there are a large number of computer programs used to practice all types of speech activity, as well as to work on all aspects of a foreign language (grammar, vocabulary, phonetics). The most common of them are **Lingualo, Duolingo, LingQ, Busuu, Bridge To English, Professor Higgins**, etc. Therefore, the teacher does not experience any difficulties in choosing one or another program to work with students, including in high school. Thus, the competence of a teacher when working with information and communication technologies includes: lesson planning, interaction with colleagues, interaction with parents, searching for educational materials on the Internet, monitoring student development, as well as extracurricular activities.²

¹ Solidjonov, D. Z. O. (2021). The impact of the development of internet technologies on education at pandemic time in Uzbekistan. In СТУДЕНТ ГОДА 2021 (pp. 108-110).

² Solidjonov, D. Z. (2021). The impact of social media on education: advantage and disadvantage. Экономика и социум, (3-1), 284-288.

The use of information and communication technologies affects students in the following way: it forms the skills of independent productive activity, helps to create a situation of success for each student, helps to increase cognitive interest in the subject, helps to understand more complex material, helps to prove oneself in a new role, affects the growth of academic performance students in the subject for the better. But, despite all the advantages, it is also worth paying attention to the weaknesses of the use of information and communication technologies in English lessons. Firstly, an English teacher may have a poor command of the basics of working with a computer, which can significantly affect the course of the lesson, thereby disrupting it. Secondly, the frequent use of these resources in the classroom can lead from developmental learning to visual and illustrative methods. And, thirdly, it is difficult to integrate a computer into the lesson structure of classes.

Interactive audio and video allow real time communication using phones and computer at the English lessons. Voice over Internet Protocol enables a person's voice to be transmitted through an Internet connection. Voice and multimedia presentations can also be delivered to a dispersed class with questions and answers taking place in realtime. Information technology has widened access to education. By the mid-1990s, many universities had begun using computers to provide classes remotely. Since then, rising numbers of adults have used online education to earn college credits. Information technology makes education available to a wider range of learners. Teachers who use classroom computers for project-based or differentiated instruction reach students with different learning styles. Teachers also use computers to provide adapted lessons for students with disabilities. Online education assists adult learners as well, by allowing people with full-time jobs and family responsibilities to obtain professional certifications or college degrees. Multimedia presentation software empowers both educators and learners to organize, present and consume information in novel ways. For example, at the English lessons different presentations may be made according to the theme with the help of computer and overhead projector. In addition, advanced multimedia software can empower educators to design audio-visual narrative themes involving the student's actual participation (learning video games). Adobe Flash offers industry-standard products assisting developers in creating such applications. With advancements in

information technology like multimedia applications and interactive software, teachers can increase literacy and understanding in any subject.

Towards the end of the late 1800s, a revolution in language teaching philosophy took place that is seen by many as the dawn of modern foreign language teaching. Different methods appeared. e.g. Grammar Translation Method, The direct method, AudioLingual Method and others. ³Grammar Translation Method in terms of its inability to create communicative competence in students, began to experiment with new ways of teaching language. Basically, teachers began attempting to teach foreign languages in a way that was more similar to first language acquisition. It incorporated techniques designed to address all the areas that the Grammar Translation did not - namely oral communication, more spontaneous use of the language, and developing the ability to think in the target language. The direct method, sometimes also called natural method, is a method that refrains from using the learners' native language and just uses the target language. This method places great stress on correct pronunciation and the target language from outset. It advocates teaching of oral skills at the expense of every traditional aim of language teaching. Audio-Lingual Method is also very popular. With the advent and popularity of audio tapes, this approach ushered in the first recordings wherein the language learner could actually hear and mimic native speakers on reel-to-reel audio tapes, often used with earphones in a language lab setting. Lessons often began with a sample dialogue to be recited and memorized. Nowadays importance of information technology in educational sector is well known. Information technology helps the students as well as the teachers in studying the course material easily because of fast access. Studying the subjects with the help of online libraries and dictionaries has made grasping and increasing the knowledge easy for the students. ⁴

Lessons with audio and video components that directly engage students reach more types of learners in comparison with traditional lecture methods of teaching, encouraging more students to participate in class and raising their level of understanding. New technology also helps disabled

³ Nunan, D. (1989). *Designing tasks for the communicative classroom*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

⁴ Nunan, D. (2004). *Task based language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

or disadvantaged students participate in subjects they were once unable to join, thanks to assistive programs and devices. The ability to collaboratively edit documents from various locations is another benefit of information technology in education. For example, students and educators utilizing cloud computing to store their homework can also modify the document's access settings to allow multiple editors and contributors to participate in an assignment. This empowers educators to design work assignments for teams of students working together and, in so doing, cultivate a teamwork ethos preparing them for the workplace. Now information technology has made it easy to study as well as teach in groups or in clusters. At the English lessons with online we can be unite together to do the desired task. There different programs, games and they help learn English language. Efficient postal systems, the telephone (fixed and mobile), and various recording and playback systems based on computer technology all have a part to play in educational broadcasting in the new millennium. The Internet and its Web sites are now familiar to many students in developed countries and among educational elites elsewhere, but it remains of little significance to very many more, who lack the most basic means for subsistence.⁵

CONCLUSION

To sum up, we consider the advantages that information and communication technologies help to: improve the efficiency and quality of education; focus on modern learning goals; increase students' motivation for learning; use interconnected training in various types of speech activity; take into account the regional aspect; make classes memorable and emotional; implement an individual approach; to strengthen the independence of schoolchildren; improve the quality of visibility; make the job of the teacher easier. Thus, information technologies used in English lessons help to switch students' attention from one type of activity to another, thereby eliminating student fatigue, work takes place on constant interest and enthusiasm, each student can immediately check the correctness of his answer, which is very important for students. we may say that information technology is indivisible part of education in the twenty-first century. When used correctly in the classroom, technology can allow students to experience situations and

⁵ Richards, J., & Rodgers, T. (2004). *Approaches and methods in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

circumstances that the students of 20 years ago could only dream about. Through technology, books and figures can suddenly become alive and applicable to the real world. In addition, information technology provides an even greater avenue for interaction between teacher and students. At the English lessons different videos, exercises, games, listening drills may be done. Information technology makes learning English available to a wider range of learners as well.

References:

1. Solidjonov, D. Z. O. (2021). The impact of the development of internet technologies on education at pandemic time in Uzbekistan. In СТУДЕНТ ГОДА 2021 (pp. 108-110).
2. Solidjonov, D. Z. (2021). The impact of social media on education: advantage and disadvantage. Экономика и социум, (3-1), 284-288.
3. Nunan, D. (1989). Designing tasks for the communicative classroom. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
4. Nunan, D. (2004). Task based language teaching. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
5. Richards, J., & Rodgers, T. (2004). Approaches and methods in language teaching. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.